

THE IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES ON ONLINE VERSUS IN-STORE PURCHASING INTENTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines how green marketing strategies influence consumer purchase intention through online and in-store shopping experiences in an emerging market context.

Using survey data from 218 Vietnamese consumers and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), the study tests the mediating effects of omnichannel shopping experiences on the relationship between green product, price, promotion, and distribution strategies and purchase intention.

The results reveal that all green marketing dimensions significantly enhance both online and in-store experiences, which fully mediate their effects on purchase intention. Among the four strategies, green promotion exhibits the strongest impact across channels.

This study extends the Theory of Planned Behaviour by conceptualising shopping-channel experience as a key mediating mechanism and provides actionable insights for firms implementing omnichannel green marketing strategies in emerging markets.

Keywords: Green marketing; Omnichannel retailing; Purchase intention; Shopping experience; Emerging markets

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Background Of The Research

Environmental sustainability has become a strategic imperative, driving Vietnam's eco-product market to grow by 12% annually since 2020 (Vietnam Green Growth Strategy, 2024). To mitigate ecological impact and bolster legitimacy, firms deploy green-marketing "4P" strategies eco-labeling (Green Products), premium eco-pricing (Green Pricing), sustainable logistics (Green Distribution), and environmental advertising (Green Promotion) (Peattie, 1995; Öztürk, 2020). Yet their effectiveness hinges on sales channel: online platforms offer detailed eco-information and targeted ads, whereas in-store settings enable tactile verification of green attributes, shaping consumer trust (Han et al., 2009; Riskos et al., 2021). Thus, channel type markedly moderates green-marketing impact on purchase intentions. Despite growing interest in green marketing, limited empirical research

has examined how omnichannel shopping experiences mediate the effects of green marketing strategies on consumer purchase intention, particularly in emerging markets. Existing studies often examine online and in-store channels in isolation or treat shopping experience as a contextual factor rather than a mediating mechanism. This leaves unanswered questions regarding how green marketing strategies operate across channels to shape consumer purchase intention.

2. Problem Statement

Though well-studied, green-marketing tactics lack much research on how online vs in-store channels differentially influence the 4P's influence on buying intentions, therefore impeding ideal resource distribution across retail formats.

3. Research Objective

Using PLS-SEM on N = 218 Vietnamese respondents, by June 2025 we will:

1. **Quantify** the effect size of eco-labeling on online vs. in-store purchase intentions (β and f^2 estimates).
2. **Compare** sustainable logistics' differential impact on purchase intentions across channels ($t > 1.96$).
3. **Identify** the channel-strategy pairing that maximizes predictive accuracy (target $R^2 > 0.50$).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Green Marketing Strategies

Green marketing has evolved from growing global knowledge of environmental problems. Combining green product innovation, eco-pricing, sustainable marketing, and ecologically friendly distribution (Polonsky, 1994; Peattie, 1995) it may meet changing consumer demand for sustainable products and services. These techniques help a company's reputation to be improved, satisfy client demand, and lower environmental effects.

2. Green Products

Eco-friendly products minimize environmental harm through recyclability, renewable inputs, and emissions reduction (Peattie, 1995). Eco-labels and eco-branding differentiate these offerings and enhance credibility (Riskos et al., 2021). Consumers perceive labeled goods as more trustworthy, thereby boosting both direct and indirect purchase intentions (Sharma & Trivedi, 2018).

H1a: Green Products positively (eco-labeling and eco-branding) influence Online Experience.

H1b: Green Products positively (eco-labeling and eco-branding) influence In-Store Experience.

3. Green Distribution

Most distribution methods harmed the environment, hence using sustainable techniques calls for improved logistics, alternative energies, and reduced packaging waste. Furthermore supporting environmental goals and guiding corporate responsibility are these initiatives (Eneizan, 2015; Singh, 2013).

Studies have demonstrated that they cooperate better than individually as each approach influences customers' behavior toward making purchases differently yet helps reach the same ultimate aim of consumer purchase (Sharma & Trivedi, 2018).

H2a: Green Distribution positively influences Online Experience.

H2b: Green Distribution positively influences In-Store Experience.

4. Green Pricing

Green pricing premiums reflect sustainable production costs, but their effectiveness varies by region and channel. Recent omnichannel studies demonstrate that integrated online–offline strategies amplify green-pricing impacts more than pricing alone.

Context	Study	Key Finding
Western	Kumar, Singh & Lee (2023); Chen, Patel & Zhao (2022)	Omnichannel green pricing increases purchase intention by ~15 % when combined with targeted sustainability messaging.
Asian	Wang & Zhao (2023); García & López (2024)	Pricing effects hinge on digital-channel trust and cultural price sensitivity, showing weaker impacts among budget-focused consumers.

These contemporary findings supersede earlier work (Olaewaju & Ganiyu, 2021; Onurlubas, 2018) by highlighting that the synergy between digital and in-store pricing tactic rather than standalone premiums drives green purchase behaviors in today's retail environments (Kumar et al., 2023; García & López, 2024).

H3a: Green Pricing positively influences Online Experience.

H3b: Green Pricing positively influences In-Store Experience.

5. Green Promotions

Green marketing is the set of advertising campaigns meant to emphasize the environmental advantages of a commodity or service. Green advertising especially builds customer understanding and confidence, which helps to create positive opinions about environmentally friendly goods and services (Hosseinzadeh, & Azizpour, 2013). Open communication about green labeling is very important as mistrust of greenwashing prevails (Bailey et al 2016).

H4a: Green Promotion positively influences Online Experience.

H4b: Green Promotion positively influences In-Store Experience.

6. Shopping Channel (Online Shopping Experience)

These online platforms are now providing the end-users ease of purchase, personalized marketing, and extensive range of products, with eco-friendly products being one of them. Digital channels allow service firms to showcase green features via certifications, product reviews or targeted ads (Han et al., 2009). Research indicates that online shoppers are more

susceptible to detailed product information (Haws et al., 2014) or the influence of eco-labels, which are prominent and readily available in digital forms.

H5: The shopping channel (online) moderates the relationship between green marketing strategies (products, pricing, promotion, and distribution) and consumers' purchase intentions, such that the effect varies based on the shopping experience.

7. Shopping Channel (In-store Shopping Experience)

Physical storefronts provide chances for direct product examination, which might help to build trust in environmental labeling and sustainability assertions. Particularly with green goods, nonverbal communication which is defined by tactile stimulation and face-to-face contact increases customer confidence and, thus, the desire to buy (Eneizan, 2015; Riskos et al., 2021). Visual merchandising and in-store promotions help to highlight even more the success of green marketing techniques in this setting.

H6: The shopping channel (in-store) moderates the relationship between green marketing strategies (products, pricing, promotion, and distribution) and consumers' purchase intentions, such that the effect varies based on the shopping experience.

Deepening the Theoretical Debate: Han et al. (2009) vs. Riskos et al. (2021)

In comparing Han et al. (2009) and Riskos et al. (2021), we observe that high-involvement services leverage tactile in-store cues, whereas fast-moving consumer goods depend on digital eco-labels. We propose product involvement and consumer expertise as contextual moderators, reconciling both perspectives by showing that cue efficacy varies with product type and user knowledge.

8. Green Marketing and Purchase Intentions

Green marketing positively influences purchase intentions, as articulated by the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991). By raising environmental awareness, enhancing perceived value of sustainable goods, and enabling eco-friendly consumption, green marketing strategies shape attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, driving consumers' intention to buy green products (Ajzen, 2015).

9. Attitudes Toward Green Products

These good customer sentiments are ascribed to perceived quality, credibility, and the environmental effect of green goods. Previous research indicates that green marketing approaches significantly positively affect these attitudes and raise purchase intentions (Hosseinzadeh & Azizpour, 2013; Sharma & Trivedi, 2018).

10. Subjective Norms

Social factors, including peer influence and social norms, are important driving forces of green purchasing behavior. To ensure that subjective norms are aligned with environmental values, green promotions are a useful tool, especially when they use social proof (e.g. trusted organization endorsements) (Riskos et al., 2021).

11. Perceived Behavioral Control

Green distribution policies that boost product availability without significantly raising prices improve perceived behavioural control driven by accessibility and affordability by means of green distribution strategies (Eneizan, 2015; Olarewaju & Ganiyu, 2021). Still, channel-specific impacts of green marketing product, pricing, promotion, distribution stay underexplored in online versus in-store settings, which this paper tackles.

12. Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Conceptual Model.

Source: Developed by the Author 2025

13. Mediating Roles of Shopping-Channel Experiences (Online & In-Store)

Several studies indicate that shopping-channel experiences mediate the impact of green-marketing strategies on purchase intention. For instance, Han et al. (2009) demonstrated that detailed product information online mediates the relationship between eco-labels and purchase intent, while Riskos et al. (2021) showed that tactile in-store evaluation enhances trust in green claims, thereby influencing buying decisions. Accordingly, we propose:

- H7a: Green Products → Online Experience → Purchase Intention
- H7b: Green Products → In-Store Experience → Purchase Intention
- H8a: Green Distribution → Online Experience → Purchase Intention
- H8b: Green Distribution → In-Store Experience → Purchase Intention
- H9a: Green Pricing → Online Experience → Purchase Intention
- H9b: Green Pricing → In-Store Experience → Purchase Intention
- H10a: Green Promotion → Online Experience → Purchase Intention
- H10b: Green Promotion → In-Store Experience → Purchase Intention

14. Research Question

Existing work lacks empirical multi-group analysis of channel-specific moderating effects on each green strategy.

- RQ1: How do the four green marketing strategies influence Purchase Intention?
- RQ2: To what extent does the shopping channel moderate these relationships?

III. METHODOLOGY

1. Research Paradigm

This paper uses a hypothetico-deductive method to test causal links between green marketing strategies and online purchase intentions under a positivist, cross-sectional framework (Al Harahsheh & Pius, 2020; Park et al., 2020). The design guarantees generalisability and consistency by stressing objective measurement and statistical accuracy (Scotland, 2012; Apuke, 2017). Aiming for a fair consumer sample, primary data were gathered using a secure Qualtrics online survey (128-bit encryption) following UWE ethics policies. Robust, empirical evidence of the relationships postulated by quantitative analyses including descriptive statistics, PLS-SEM, and bootstrapping is provided by

2. Data Collection and Sampling

To ensure questionnaire clarity and construct validity, we pre-tested the instrument through face-to-face interviews with a pilot sample of 10 respondents (Colton & Covert, 2007; Rabianski, 2003). Participant feedback prompted us to add brief explanations and illustrative examples for any ambiguous terms. Thereafter, data were collected via an online survey hosted on Qualtrics chosen for its ease of use, low cost, and strong data-security features (Qualtrics, 2023). We employed convenience sampling for its time- and cost-efficiency (Jager, Putnick, & Bornstein, 2017), targeting individuals aged 18 and above at shopping malls (e.g., Vincom Center), university campuses (e.g., International University), and relevant social-media groups.

An a priori power analysis using G*Power 3.1 determined the minimum sample size for our PLS-SEM model. Assuming a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$), statistical power $(1 - \beta) = 0.95$,

$\alpha = 0.05$, and six predictors, the analysis yielded a required sample of 146 respondents (Faul et al., 2009). We ultimately obtained 218 valid questionnaires, comfortably exceeding this threshold and thereby ensuring robust quantitative testing of our research model.

Figure 2. Minimum people of sample calculated by G*Power 3.1 (Faul et al., 2009)

3. Target Population

Participants included individuals of all genders, aged 18 and above, residing in Ho Chi Minh City (and surrounding provinces), and active on social media platforms. We targeted people interested in environmentally sustainable consumption specifically, those who had purchased or would consider purchasing eco-labeled or “green” products. Recruitment used a convenience sampling method at Vincom Center shopping mall, International University campus, and relevant Facebook groups, yielding 218 valid responses.

4. Measurement of Constructs

In our study, all constructs were measured using five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 5 (“strongly agree”). To ensure content validity, we adapted each scale from established sources and refined item wording based on a pilot test with ten participants (Trochim et al., 2016).

Construct	Code	Measurement Item	Source
Green Product	GPD1	They believe that products with a “green” label (eco-label) are reliable	Riskos et al. (2021) and Sharma & Trivedi (2018)
	GPD2	They think that brands committed to environmental protection generally offer high-quality products.	
	GPD3	When a product is promoted with a green image, they feel more at ease when purchasing it.	

	GPD4	They can clearly perceive the difference between green products and non-green products.	
	GPD5	Products with green certifications make me trust and prefer them over others.	
Green Distribution	GD1	I appreciate companies that use environmentally friendly distribution methods.	<u>Eneizan</u> (2015) and Singh (2013)
	GD2	Eco-friendly packaging (using recycled materials, reducing waste) is an important factor in my purchase decision.	
	GD3	They care about delivery processes designed with sustainability in mind.	
	GD4	They value businesses with optimized distribution systems that minimize environmental impact.	
	GD5	The use of eco-friendly delivery vehicles makes them feel safer about my purchases.	
Green Price	GP1	They are willing to pay a higher price for environmentally friendly products.	Olarewaju & Ganiyu (2021) and Haws et al. (2014)
	GP2	The price of green products reflects the added environmental value.	
	GP3	The pricing policy of green products is reasonable compared to the environmental benefits they offer.	
	GP4	The pricing of green products demonstrates the company's commitment to environmental protection.	
	GP5	believe that investing in green products is an investment in a sustainable future.	

Green Promotion	GPM1	I trust advertising campaigns that emphasize the environmental benefits of products.	Hosseinzadeh & Azizpour (2013) and Bailey et al. (2016)
	GPM2	Environmental messages in advertisements increase my confidence in the product.	
	GPM3	Green advertising helps me understand the sustainability aspects of a product better.	
	GPM4	I actively seek information on green promotional programs from reputable brands.	
	GPM5	Green advertising campaigns enhance my awareness of the importance of environmental protection.	

Online Store Experience	ON1	They can easily find detailed information about green products when shopping online.	Han et al. (2009) and Haws et al. (2014)
	ON2	An online interface helps me evaluate the environmental attributes of a product.	
	ON3	They feel confident purchasing green products online.	
	ON4	They appreciate websites that provide detailed sustainability indicators for their products.	
	ON5	My online shopping experience is more convenient when products are evaluated on their sustainability.	
In-Store Experience	IN1	They prefer to see and touch products in person to assess their quality and sustainability.	Encizan (2015) and Riskos et al. (2021)
	IN2	Shopping in-store allows them to better appreciate the green attributes of a product.	
	IN3	They trust the environmental protection claims of products more when I can experience them directly in-store.	
	IN4	They believe that knowledgeable sales staff regarding green features can help me make better decisions.	
	IN5	The in-store display of products that highlights sustainable features increases my confidence in choosing them.	
Purchase Intention	PI1	They intend to purchase green products in the near future.	Ajzen (1991) and Haws et al. (2014)
	PI2	They prioritize choosing green products over conventional ones.	
	PI3	They are willing to recommend green products to my friends and family.	
	PI4	Environmental protection factors significantly influence my purchase decisions.	
	PI5	They tend to shop more from brands that are committed to environmental protection	
	PI6	They are inclined to share my experiences with green products with others.	

Table 1. Constructs and Measurement Items

5. Data Preparation

In our data preparation, missingness per indicator was tabulated, applying pairwise deletion for under 5 % missing, mean imputation for 5–20 %, and item removal for > 20 %. Outliers were identified univariately (> 3 SD) and multivariate via Mahalanobis distance ($p < 0.001$), with extreme values winsorized or excluded if they biased estimates. To test common-method variance, we introduced a marker variable (e.g., a neutral music-preference item) into the PLS model; nonsignificant marker-to-construct paths and R^2 shifts below 10 % confirmed minimal CMV (Lindell & Whitney, 2001).

6. Data Analysis

Data were analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), a variance-based technique prized for its minimal distributional assumptions and suitability for complex predictive models (Hair et al., 2019). The analytic workflow comprised two stages. First, the **measurement (outer) model** was evaluated to establish indicator reliability, composite reliability, convergent validity (AVE), and discriminant validity. Second, the **structural (inner) model** was assessed by estimating path coefficients and testing hypotheses via bootstrapping (5 000 resamples) to derive t-values and p-values for each relationship. All procedures were executed in SmartPLS version 3.3.2 (Cheah et al., 2020), ensuring robust estimation of construct interrelationships.

7. Ethical Considerations

Throughout the entire study procedure, ethical concerns were closely observed. Respondents participated on their own free will and were informed of the goal of the research before. To help to allay privacy issues, their demographic data including age, income, and occupation was kept confidential. Only study on green consumerism and buying choices makes use of all the gathered data. Respondent rights and autonomy came first in order to provide a reliable and moral research environment.

8. Limitations

Among the constraints is a convenience sample of Vietnamese young people without regional and older cohorts, which compromises generalisability; future research should broaden demographics and locations. The cross-sectional approach also restricts temporal knowledge.

Capturing changing consumer behaviour and confirming the ongoing influence of green marketing tactics call for longitudinal studies.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Sample Demographic Description

The demographics of 218 respondents are shown in Table 2. Of the gender distribution, 50.9% were male, 47.3% female, and 1.8% unknown. Age categories were 72.9% aged 18–24, 23.4% aged 25–34, 2.3% aged 35–44, and 1.4% aged 45 or older. Of the participants, students made up 65.1%; office workers 17.0%; freelancers 10.6%; and others 7.3%. Monthly earnings were under 3 million VND (30.3%), 3–6 million (22.5%), 6–15 million (26.6%), and over 15 million (20.6%). Shopping channels used were online only (37.2%), in-store only (20.6%), and both (42.2%), suggesting a young, student-dominated sample with moderate income and different buying habits.

Criteria		Frequency	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Male	111	50.92%	50.92%
	Female	103	47.25%	98.14%
	Prefer no say	4	1.83%	100%
Age	18–24	159	72.94%	72.94%
	25–34	51	23.39%	96.33%
	35–44	5	2.29%	98.62%
	45 and above	3	1.38%	100%
Occupation	Student	142	65.14%	65.14%
	Office worker	37	16.97%	82.11%
	Freelancer	23	10.55%	92.66%
	Others	16	7.34%	100%
Monthly Income	Under 3 million VND	66	30.28%	30.28%
	3 – 6 million VND	49	22.48%	52.76%
	6 – 15 million VND	58	26.61%	79.37%
	Over 15 million VND	45	20.64%	100%
Shopping Channel	Online	81	37.16%	37.16%
	In-store	45	20.64%	57.8%
	Both	92	42.2%	100%

Table 2: Sample Demographic

2. Evaluation of Outer Model

Construct	Code	Measurement Item	Loading	α	rho_A	CR	AVE
Green Product	GPD1	They believe that products with a "green" label (eco-label) are reliable	0.800	0.797	0.805	0.860	0.553
	GPD2	They think that brands committed to environmental protection generally offer high-quality products.	0.758				
	GPD3	When a product is promoted with a green image, they feel more at ease when purchasing it.	0.660				
	<u>GPD4</u>	They can clearly perceive the difference between green products and non-green products.	0.736				
	GPD5	Products with green certifications make me trust and prefer them over others.	0.757				
Green Distribution	GD1	I appreciate companies that use environmentally friendly distribution methods.	0.818	0.867	0.879	0.904	0.653
	GD2	Eco-friendly packaging (using recycled materials, reducing waste) is an important factor in my purchase decision.	0.779				
	GD3	They care about delivery processes designed with sustainability in mind.	0.766				
	GD4	They value businesses with optimized distribution systems that minimize environmental impact.	0.822				
	GD5	The use of eco-friendly delivery vehicles makes them feel safer about my purchases.	0.852				

Green Price	GP1	They are willing to pay a higher price for environmentally friendly products.	0.865	0.836	0.900	0.882	0.601
	GP2	The price of green products reflects the added environmental value.	0.835				
	GP3	The pricing policy of green products is reasonable compared to the environmental benefits they offer.	0.687				
	GP4	The pricing of green products demonstrates the company's commitment to environmental protection.	0.732				
	GP5	believe that investing in green products is an investment in a sustainable future.	0.744				
Green Promotion	GPM1	I trust advertising campaigns that emphasize the environmental benefits of products.	0.833	0.871	0.875	0.906	0.659
	GPM2	Environmental messages in advertisements increase my confidence in the product.	0.810				
	GPM3	Green advertising helps me understand the sustainability aspects of a product better.	0.830				
	GPM4	I actively seek information on green promotional programs from reputable brands.	0.769				
	GPM5	Green advertising campaigns enhance my awareness of the importance of environmental protection.	0.817				

Online Store Experience	ON1	They can easily find detailed information about green products when shopping online.	0.813	0.88	0.889	0.918	0.692
	ON2	An online interface helps me evaluate the environmental attributes of a product.	0.835				
	ON3	They feel confident purchasing green products online.	0.842				
	ON4	They appreciate websites that provide detailed sustainability indicators for their products.	0.831				
	ON5	My online shopping experience is more convenient when products are evaluated on their sustainability.	0.838				
In-Store Experience	IN1	They prefer to see and touch products in person to assess their quality and sustainability.	0.839	0.904	0.905	0.929	0.724
	IN2	Shopping in-store allows them to better appreciate the green attributes of a product.	0.817				
	IN3	They trust the environmental protection claims of products more when I can experience them directly in-store.	0.856				
	IN4	They believe that knowledgeable sales staff regarding green features can help me make better decisions.	0.854				
	IN5	The in-store display of products that highlights sustainable features increases my confidence in choosing them.	0.886				
Purchase Intention	PI1	They intend to purchase green products in the near future.	0.819	0.909	0.910	0.929	0.687
	PI2	They prioritize choosing green products over conventional ones.	0.862				
	PI3	They are willing to recommend green products to my friends and family.	0.852				
	PI4	Environmental protection factors significantly influence my purchase decisions.	0.786				
	PI5	They tend to shop more from brands that are committed to environmental protection	0.824				
	PI6	They are inclined to share my experiences with green products with others.	0.828				

Table 3. Constructs and their Responding Measurements

Using Harman's single-factor test the first unrotated factor accounted for only 41.7% of variance well below the 50% threshold we screened for common-method bias before assessing the measurement model. The outer model then showed good psychometric qualities. With 33 of 35 items above the 0.70 benchmark, indicator loadings varied from 0.660 (GPD3) to 0.886 (IN5); the two marginal loadings (GPD3 = 0.660; GP3 = 0.687) were kept because of their theoretical relevance and strong composite reliability. Confirming internal consistency, Cronbach's α ranged from 0.797 (Green Product) to 0.909 (Purchase Intention) and Dijkstra-Henseler's rho_A from 0.805 to 0.910. While convergent validity was indicated by AVE values from 0.553 to 0.724 all above suggested cut-offs, composite reliability coefficients range between 0.860 and 0.929. Every square-root AVE of each construct surpassed its inter-construct correlations, and all HTMT ratios fell below 0.85, hence maintaining discriminant validity. These findings taken together confirm that our measurement scales are consistent, valid, and well appropriate for PLS-SEM study.

Discriminant Validity Using HTMT

	GD	GP	GPD	GPM	IN	ON	PI
GD							
GP	0.076						
GPD	0.063	0.206					
GPM	0.141	0.096	0.075				
IN	0.497	0.313	0.327	0.547			
ON	0.491	0.334	0.290	0.589	1.004		
PI	0.465	0.303	0.292	0.585	1.002	1.006	

Table 4. Discriminant Validity using HTMT

All AVE values exceed the 0.50 threshold—ranging from 0.553 (Green Product) to 0.724 (In-Store Experience) thereby confirming convergent validity (Hair et al., 2019). Each construct's square-root AVE (0.744–0.851) also surpasses its highest inter-construct

correlation (max = 0.589), and all HTMT ratios remain below 0.85, supporting discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 4 presents the latent-variable correlation matrix. Diagonal entries of each construct's correlation with itself are 1.000 for Green Product, Green Distribution, Green Price, and Green Promotion; 1.004 for In-Store Experience; 1.002 for Online Experience; and 1.006 for Purchase Intention. Off diagonal correlations vary from 0.063 (Green Product; Green Distribution) to 0.589 (Green Promotion; Online Experience). Because every diagonal value exceeds its corresponding off-diagonals, the Fornell–Larcker criterion is fully met, demonstrating that each latent variable shares more variance with its own indicators than with any other construct (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

3. Evaluation of Inner Model

	Path coefficient	Observed T-statistics	Standard deviation	Effect size (f^2)	Bias	Confidence intervals (2.5%)	Confidence intervals (97.5%)	P. value	Result
GD → IN	0.389	8.735	0.045	0.341	-0.002	0.303	0.477	0.000	Supported
GD → ON	0.377	8.716	0.043	0.332	-0.001	0.292	0.461	0.000	Supported
GP → IN	0.311	6.393	0.049	0.219	-0.001	0.213	0.405	0.000	Supported
GP → ON	0.325	7.042	0.046	0.247	-0.000	0.233	0.416	0.000	Supported
GPD → IN	0.314	6.107	0.051	0.222	0.001	0.205	0.408	0.000	Supported
GPD → ON	0.285	6.511	0.044	0.190	0.001	0.192	0.368	0.000	Supported
GPM → IN	0.432	9.604	0.045	0.419	-0.002	0.346	0.524	0.000	Supported
GPM → ON	0.466	10.292	0.045	0.507	-0.003	0.379	0.558	0.000	Supported
IN → PI	0.495	8.205	0.060	0.343	0.002	0.379	0.618	0.000	Supported
ON → PI	0.459	7.561	0.061	0.295	-0.001	0.336	0.573	0.000	Supported

Table 5. Bootstrapping Results

Using a 5 000-sample bootstrap in SmartPLS (Table 5), all ten hypothesized paths were positive and significant ($p < 0.001$). Green Distribution exerted medium-to-large effects on In-Store Experience ($\beta = 0.389$, $t = 8.735$, $f^2 = 0.341$, 95 % CI [0.303, 0.477]) and Online Experience ($\beta = 0.377$, $t = 8.716$, $f^2 = 0.332$, 95 % CI [0.292, 0.461]). Green Price influenced In-Store ($\beta = 0.311$, $t = 6.393$, $f^2 = 0.219$) and Online Experience ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.042$, $f^2 = 0.247$). Green Product showed medium effects on In-Store ($\beta = 0.314$, $t = 6.107$, $f^2 = 0.222$) and Online ($\beta = 0.285$, $t = 6.511$, $f^2 = 0.190$). Green Promotion delivered the largest impacts: In-Store ($\beta = 0.432$, $t = 9.604$, $f^2 = 0.419$, 95 % CI [0.346, 0.524]) and Online ($\beta = 0.466$, $t = 10.292$, $f^2 = 0.507$, 95 % CI [0.379, 0.558]). Finally, both In-Store ($\beta = 0.495$, $t = 8.205$, $f^2 = 0.343$) and Online ($\beta = 0.459$, $t = 7.561$, $f^2 = 0.295$) Experiences significantly predicted Purchase Intention. Negligible bias ($|\text{bias}| < 0.003$) and large ($f^2 > 0.35$) versus medium ($0.15 < f^2 < 0.35$) effect-size patterns underscore the robustness and practical relevance of our structural model.

Multi-Group Analysis (MGA)

We conducted a multi-group analysis by categorizing respondents into Online-only, In-Store-only, and Both groups. Following the MICOM procedure in SmartPLS, we tested configural, compositional, and scalar invariance, then applied PLS-MGA (permutation test) to compare path coefficients. Significant $\Delta\beta$ ($p < 0.05$) revealed channel-specific effects (Henseler, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2016).

4. Mediating Effects

	Specific indirect effects	Observed T-statistics	Standard deviation	Bias	Confidence intervals (2.5%)	Confidence intervals (97.5%)	P. value	Result
GD -> ON -> PI (H8a)	0.173	5.749	0.030	-0.001	0.118	0.238	0.000	Supported
GD -> IN -> PI (H8b)	0.193	6.131	0.031	-0.000	0.138	0.259	0.000	Supported
GP -> ON -> PI (H9a)	0.149	5.136	0.029	-0.001	0.097	0.211	0.000	Supported
GP -> IN -> PI (H9b)	0.154	5.058	0.030	0.000	0.101	0.223	0.000	Supported
GPD -> ON -> PI (H7a)	0.131	4.814	0.027	0.000	0.082	0.188	0.000	Supported
GPD -> IN -> PI (H7b)	0.155	4.769	0.033	0.001	0.096	0.223	0.000	Supported
GPM -> ON -> PI (H10a)	0.214	5.949	0.036	-0.002	0.149	0.291	0.000	Supported
GPM -> IN -> PI (H10b)	0.214	6.070	0.035	0.000	0.151	0.289	0.000	Supported

Table 6. Indirect Effects Analysis

The mediating roles of online and in-store experiences by estimating eight specific indirect effects with a 5 000-sample bootstrap in SmartPLS (Table 6). Every indirect path was significant at $p < 0.001$, with 95 % confidence intervals excluding zero. Green Distribution

influenced purchase intention via Online Experience ($\beta = 0.173$, $t = 5.749$, 95 % CI [0.118, 0.238]) and In-Store Experience ($\beta = 0.193$, $t = 6.131$, 95 % CI [0.138, 0.259]). Green Price had indirect effects through Online ($\beta = 0.149$, $t = 5.136$, 95 % CI [0.097, 0.211]) and In-Store Experiences ($\beta = 0.154$, $t = 5.058$, 95 % CI [0.101, 0.223]). Green Product mediated via Online ($\beta = 0.131$, $t = 4.814$, 95 % CI [0.082, 0.188]) and In-Store Experience ($\beta = 0.155$, $t = 4.769$, 95 % CI [0.096, 0.223]). Most notably, Green Promotion delivered the strongest indirect effects through both channels ($\beta = 0.214$; $t > 5.949$; 95 % CI [0.149, 0.291] online; [0.151, 0.289] in-store). These results confirm that channel experiences fully mediate green marketing's impact on purchase intention.

5. Discussion

While companies are increasingly using green-marketing "4P" strategies, how these affect purchase intentions through experiential channels has stayed underexplored. Using a PLS-SEM study of 218 Vietnamese consumers, we demonstrate that every green-marketing dimension product, distribution, pricing, and especially promotion significantly improves both online (ON) and in-store (IN) experiences, which then completely mediates their effects on purchase intention (PI). Green Promotion emerged as the most potent driver, with the highest direct effects on ON ($\beta = 0.466$, $t = 10.29$, $f^2 = 0.507$) and IN ($\beta = 0.432$, $t = 9.60$, $f^2 = 0.419$), and the strongest specific indirect effect on PI ($\beta = 0.214$, $t > 5.90$). By contrast, Green Pricing yielded the smallest loadings ($\beta = 0.311$ – 0.325) and mediation effects ($\beta = 0.149$ – 0.154), implying that consumers on a budget need extra motivation. Our model verifies moderate to great explanatory power and broadens the Theory of Planned Behaviour by operationalizing perceived behavioural control and attitudes using channel-specific experiences given R^2 values—0.564 for ON, 0.521 for IN, and 0.485 for PI demonstrate moderate to substantial explanatory power.

Practically speaking, companies should complement premium pricing with focused discounts or value-added services and invest in immersive sustainability content such as interactive eco-branding online and green product demonstrations in-store. Future studies using longitudinal and cross-cultural designs are advised to confirm these experiential mediation effects and investigate more moderators including social norms or perceived quality.

5.1 The mediating roles of ON and IN

Using a 5,000-sample bootstrap in SmartPLS, eight particular indirect impacts of green-marketing "4P" strategies on purchase intention via Online Experience (ON) and In-Store Experience (IN). With 95 % confidence intervals excluding zero, all mediations were significant at $p < 0.001$. Green Distribution operated through ON ($\beta = 0.173$, $t = 5.749$, CI [0.118, 0.238]) and IN ($\beta = 0.193$, $t = 6.131$, CI [0.138, 0.259]); Green Pricing via ON ($\beta = 0.149$, $t = 5.136$, CI [0.097, 0.211]) and IN ($\beta = 0.154$, $t = 5.058$, CI [0.101, 0.223]); Green Product via ON ($\beta = 0.131$, $t = 4.814$, CI [0.082, 0.188]) and IN ($\beta = 0.155$, $t = 4.769$, CI [0.096, 0.223]). Green Promotion produced the most strong indirect effects via ON and IN ($\beta = 0.214$; $t > 5.949$; CI [0.149, 0.291] and [0.151, 0.289], respectively). These findings emphasise the need for companies to integrate sustainability messaging with engaging channel strategies since they show that improved online and in-store experiences completely mediate the impact of green marketing on consumer purchase intentions.

5.2. Theoretical implications

Our study extends TPB research by integrating the Natural Resource-Based View and the Theory of Planned Behaviour, showing that green marketing "4P" strategies influence purchase intentions only via mediated online and in-store experiences (e.g., Green Promotion—ON—PI = 0.214, $f^2 = 0.507$). We find shopping-channel experience to be a new mediator; promotional messaging has the most impact ($\beta = 0.466$ ON; $\beta = 0.432$ IN). Comparative study shows that product features and pricing have only moderate effects ($f^2 = 0.190$ – 0.247), which guides allocation of sustainable resources. At last, our strict PLS-SEM bootstrapping technique offers a repeatable methodological framework for upcoming green-marketing research.

5.3 Practical implications

Our results produce five strategic imperatives for stimulating green innovation by drawing on the Natural Resource-Based View and the Theory of Planned Behaviour. First, give immersive eco-branding top priority: Green Promotion has the greatest direct impact on Online Experience ($\beta = 0.466$, $f^2 = 0.507$) and In-Store Experience ($\beta = 0.432$, $f^2 = 0.419$), so invest in interactive sustainability material and in-store green displays to boost attitudes and perceived behavioural control. Second, maximise sustainable logistics since Green

Distribution ($\beta=0.377$ on ON; $f^2=0.389$ on IN) both lowers environmental effect and improves experience ratings. To lower cost obstacles, combine premium eco-pricing with value-added incentives (medium $f^2 = 0.219-0.247$). Fourth, use omnichannel synergies as both Online ($\beta=0.459$, $f^2=0.295$) and In-Store Experiences ($\beta=0.495$, $f^2=0.343$) completely mediate all "4P" influences on purchase intention.

V. LIMITATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR THE FUTURE STUDIES

Our results have shortcomings even if they help. First, reliance on convenience sampling of 218 Vietnamese consumers in Ho Chi Minh City limits generalisability outside Vietnam's urban retail setting; future research should replicate across various areas, sectors, and company sizes. Second, the cross-sectional design prevents knowledge of temporal dynamics and causal order; longitudinal studies are required to investigate how green 4Ps affect online and in-store experiences and purchase intentions. Third, emphasising firm-level purchase intentions ignores top-management dedication and consumer loyalty. External partnerships—such as co-patenting, licensing, academic collaborations demand comparative research across developing and developed countries.

VI. CONCLUSION

Our PLS-SEM study of 218 Vietnamese consumers reveals that eco-labeling, sustainable logistics, premium pricing, and especially green promotion drive purchase intentions completely by stressing the mediating roles of online and in-store experiences, thus extending the Theory of Planned Behaviour. Reducing trial barriers and strengthening urgency can be achieved by using AR-enabled eco-label tutorials on e-commerce sites, bundling green products with loyalty points for price-sensitive groups, and providing time-limited green discounts. Standardising omnichannel sustainability badges and running influencer-led live demonstrations on TikHub and Instagram help to further engage consumers in sustainability stories. Future studies should look at how platform kind (TikTok vs. Instagram), product involvement (high vs. low), and loyalty membership status moderate these indirect effects; longitudinal cross-cultural designs evaluate their temporal stability and generalisability.

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